

Predicting Phase-Transfer Behavior of Gold Nanoparticles with UV-VIS Spectroscopy

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Abstract: UV-VIS spectroscopy is used to investigate aqueous gold nanoparticle (AuNP) solutions with respect to their ability to be transferred into chloroform using 1-dodecanethiol. Five reverse Turkevick syntheses using different ratios of citric acid/gold are used to prepare AuNP. UV-VIS monitors the different syntheses at the wavelength of maximum absorbance (525 nm), and spectra of the final products are acquired. It is shown that the solutions that develop color slowly and have smaller absorbance at 525 nm are more likely to undergo successful phase transfer in chloroform with the addition of 1-dodecanethiol. The work suggests that using UV-VIS to measure the appearance of color during the synthesis of AuNP may be an efficient method for predicting the behavior of the nanoparticles concerning various reactions or applications.

Keywords: gold nanoparticles; phase-transfer; chloroform; 1-dodecanethiol; UV-VIS spectroscopy

1. Introduction

Turkevick or reverse Turkevick reactions produce aqueous solutions of AuNP by the reduction of gold ions with a variety of reducing agents [1-3]. The size, shape, and concentration of the nanoparticles obtained is a function of a large number of experimental variables, which include the volume, concentration, and identity of the reducing agent, the volume and concentration of the gold, the method and rate of mixing of these reagents, the time, temperature, pH, and stirring speed of the reaction, the use of a capping reagent, and even the aspect ratio of the mixing vessel [2-4]. It is not always trivial to reproduce a published synthesis with respect to the size of the product, and it is not unusual to encounter reproducibility issues for syntheses done in the same lab.

Typically, the AuNP product is characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), or dynamic light scattering (DLS) [5-9]. SEM and TEM provide images of the particles, while DLS provides size and statistics that describe size distribution. The size and shape of the nanoparticles affect their ability to undergo subsequent reactions, such as phase transfer in which the particles are moved from an aqueous solution into a nonpolar solvent by means of a surfactant or phase transfer reagent [10].

The initial goal of our work was to synthesize AuNP and transfer them from an aqueous solution into chloroform using 1-dodecanethiol. This phase transfer into chloroform has been accomplished by others using a variety of sizes of AuNP and several different surfactants [10-11]. The ability to transfer the nanoparticles into non-polar solvents is a prerequisite for using them to detect analytes that are not water soluble [12] and beneficial in the employment of nanoparticles for drug delivery and imaging [13-18].

While we were able to achieve the transfer in many instances, the results of seemingly identical experiments were not always consistent – sometimes the particles would transfer, and sometimes they would not. DLS indicated that size reproducibility was a potential issue. Smaller nanoparticles were more likely to transfer than larger ones. Using

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DLS to screen the product of our synthesis for the potential to undergo phase transfer allowed us to conserve time and reagents by foregoing attempts to transfer the particles that appeared too large.

Through the course of this work, it was also observed that the temporal evolution of color during the synthesis itself (clear, to grey/purple, to pink, to red) was a good predictor of the ability of the AuNP to undergo subsequent phase transfer. Certainly, the color is related to size, so this observation is not surprising [19]. The literature also suggests that the colors observed correspond to distinct processes in the growth of the nanoparticles: nucleation (clear), growth into larger structures - perhaps nanowires (grey/purple), and cleavage of the larger structures to produce small spheres (pink or red) [20]. Because the kinetics of these processes dictates the ultimate size of the AuNP, it is also not surprising that the time it takes for the color changes to occur correlates with the size of the particles produced. Other factors, such as concentration and degree of aggregation, also affect the color. In our experiments, it was not unusual for the same procedure to yield products that showed slight differences in the evolution of color and final color. Rather than using DLS or microscopy to analyze the products of each synthesis, we investigated the relationship between the evolution of color, the final color, and the ability to transfer the AuNP into chloroform.

In this work, we present not only the procedure for synthesis and phase transfer of the AuNP into chloroform using 1-dodecanethiol but also the results of the spectroscopic monitoring of the synthesis to predict their "transferability." We use a reverse Turkevick method for the reduction of a gold solution with citric acid with 1% polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) added, and we use 1-dodecanethiol as a phase transfer reagent to move the particles into chloroform. The spectroscopic data obtained during the synthesis allows us to predict if the AuNP will undergo phase transfer. This spectroscopic monitoring eliminated the need for characterization by microscopy or light scattering. It allowed us to save time and chemicals by eliminating attempts to transfer particles that were predicted to fail. Monitoring the temporal evolution of color in AuNP synthesis may be an efficient quality control technique for other applications and nanoparticles other than gold.

2. Materials and Methods

Synthesis of Gold Nanoparticles

Solutions of 1.08 mM (0.025 % w/v, metal basis) chloroauric acid (HAuCl_4), 2.38 mM (0.05 % w/v) citric acid ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_7$), and 1% w/v polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) were prepared from 1% gold chloride solution (Sigma), solid citric acid (Fisher), and PVP (avg. mol. wt. 40,000, Sigma) in nanopure water using successive dilutions as necessary. 1-dodecanethiol (Oakwood Chemical) and chloroform (99%, Sigma) were used for the phase transfer. DLS was performed on an in-house instrument consisting of a 20 mW HeNe laser (Newport), an autocorrelator (Brookhaven Instruments, B1-DS1), and a temperature-controlled sample holder (Quantum-Northwest). Samples were equilibrated to 20°C, and the scattered light was detected at 73.7° relative to the incident laser beam. The UV-VIS spectrometer used was an Evolution 300 (Thermo Scientific).

The reverse Turkevick method was used for synthesis. To begin, 20 mL of the 2.38 mM citric acid with 200 μL of 1% PVP was brought to boiling in a 50 mL beaker under constant stirring with a 15 mm Teflon stir bar at approximately 250 rpm. Then, 1.08 mM HAuCl_4 was added all at once. Various volumes of 1.08 mM HAuCl_4 were added in a series of syntheses. These volumes included 1.0 mL, 1.5 mL, 2.0 mL, 2.5 mL, and 3.0 mL. After the addition of gold, the heating was turned off, and the reaction continued to stir. The various volumes of gold used resulted in different citric acid/gold mole ratios, resulting in different products, as evident by DLS and the different final colors of solution. It is important to note that because the citric acid was constant and the ratio is expressed as citric acid/gold, the smaller mole ratios result from using more gold. The experiments

conducted using the 5 different volumes of gold solution are summarized in Table 1. DLS and UV-VIS characterized the AuNP produced by each of these syntheses.

Table 1. The volumes of reagents and the mole ratio (citric acid/gold) for the five reverse Turkevick syntheses.

Volume of 1.08 mM AuCl	Volume of 2.38 mM C ₆ H ₈ O ₇	Mole Ratio (citric acid/gold)
1.0 ml	20 ml	44.1
1.5 ml	20 ml	29.4
2.0 ml	20 ml	22.0
2.5 ml	20 ml	17.6
3.0 ml	20 ml	14.7

Phase Transfer of Gold Nanoparticles

Although the nanoparticles synthesized appeared stable in an aqueous solution, all nanoparticle solutions were tested for phase transfer within 72 hours of synthesis. In order to transfer the nanoparticles into chloroform, 5.0 mL of aqueous nanoparticle solution was combined with 100 μ L of 1-dodecanethiol in a 20 ml glass vial. Then, 5.0 mL of chloroform was added to the vial using a glass pipette. The vial was capped and vigorously shaken by hand for 30 seconds. After this time, the vial was placed on the bench, and the water and chloroform were allowed to settle into separate layers. Theoretically, the 1-dodecanethiol encapsulates the metal nanoparticle with the thiol group nearest the metal and the alkyl group, providing a hydrophobic coating and allowing the particle to transfer from water to chloroform. In practice, movement of the red color from the top (aqueous) layer to the bottom (chloroform) layer was taken as evidence that the transfer was successful.

Spectroscopic Monitoring of the Synthesis

Because it was observed that the temporal evolution of color seemed to be useful in predicting whether nanoparticles would transfer, an experiment was designed to measure this evolution of color during the synthesis. Specifically, an adjustable flow liquid pump (Kamoer) was used to pump the solution from the reaction vial through a 4 ml flow-through cuvette placed in the UV-VIS spectrometer. The flow rate was approximately 100 ml/min. The spectrometer was set to measure absorption at the surface plasmon resonance of 525 nm, taking an absorption measurement every minute. The synthesis was conducted as described above, and the spectrometer began data acquisition when the gold solution was added to the citric acid. As the solution changed from clear, to grey/purple, to pink/red, the absorption at 525 increased. Regardless of the mole ratio of citric acid/gold used in the synthesis, the absorption became almost constant after about 15 minutes. A plot of absorption at 525 nm vs. time was obtained for each synthetic experiment.

3. Results

The five synthetic experiments using different mole ratios resulted in the five solutions shown in Figure 1. As the mole ratio of citric acid/gold increases, the color becomes lighter. The UV-VIS spectra of each of the solutions are shown in Figure 2. Raw data for Figure 2 is included in *Supplementary Materials*. The spectra indicate that the wavelength of maximum absorption is almost constant at 525 nm. The solution with a mole ratio of 14.7 showed maximum absorption at 527 nm. All the other solutions showed maxima at 525 nm. The size of the nanoparticles obtained by DLS was between 18-30 nm for all solutions. Still, the polydispersity made it impossible to establish the relationship between mole fraction and particle size. The fact that the wavelength of maximum absorption in the UV-VIS spectra does not change significantly is evidence that the particles from each

synthesis do not vary dramatically in size. The most significant difference would appear to be the concentration.

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Figure 1. The solutions obtained from the five syntheses described in Table 1. The numbers are the mole ratios (citric acid/gold).

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Figure 2. The UV-VIS spectra of the solutions from the five syntheses described in Table 1. The numbers in the legend are the mole ratios (citric acid/gold).

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With respect to transferring into chloroform, the results can be seen in Figure 3. The darker-colored solutions (i.e., mole ratios 14.7 and 17.6) showed aggregation of particles upon attempting transfer into chloroform, as evident by the difference in color between the particles in the aqueous layer (before) and the chloroform layer (after). The less concentrated solutions (i.e., mole ratios 29.4 and 44.1) transferred successfully into chloroform without aggregation, as evident by the fact that there was no color change. Based on this data, measuring absorption at 525 nm (A_{525}) would be useful to predict which aqueous nanoparticle solutions would transfer successfully to chloroform. In these experiments, solutions with $A_{525} < 0.25$ transferred; solutions with $A_{525} > 0.25$ did not.

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Figure 3. The bi-phasic solutions before and after transfer of AuNP into chloroform.

The results of monitoring absorption at 525 nm during the synthesis of the AuNP are shown in Figure 4. The raw data for these curves can be found in the *Supplementary Materials*. The absorption increased over the course of the 14 minutes during which the synthesis was monitored. By the end of 14 minutes, the absorption was approaching its maximum. In practice, differences between the solutions became evident early in the reaction. For example, the solution with the most gold (ratio = 14.7) turned from clear to grey about 3 minutes into the reaction. The A_{525} increased between 3 and 10 minutes quickly, and after 14 minutes, the solution had the darker red color shown in Figure 3 for a mole ratio of 14.7. A video of a similar reaction is included in the *Supplementary Materials*. The plot of A_{525} vs. time for this experiment was “S-shaped,” the maximum absorption was > 0.3 , and ultimately the particles produced from this synthesis did not transfer into chloroform. In contrast, the solution with the least gold (ratio = 44.1) took on a very faint pink color early in the reaction and developed color very slowly throughout the reaction. The plot of A_{525} vs. time was “log-shaped,” the maximum absorption was 0.004, and the particles transferred into chloroform. Certainly, the AuNP concentration, the solution's absorption, and the ability to transfer into chloroform are correlated. But the spectroscopic monitoring also suggests that there may be a different process at work in forming the more concentrated solutions. The appearance of a grey color early in the reaction and the rapid increase in absorption around 3 minutes is due to the formation of larger structures- perhaps “nanowires” – that subsequently disintegrate to give nanospheres with the characteristic pink color [20]. In contrast, the slower increases and log-shaped appearance of the absorbance vs. time plots would indicate a controlled assembly process rather than disintegration [20]. Regardless of the process, the spectroscopic data allows us to make reasonable predictions about the behavior of the final product. Specifically, “S-shaped” curves with rapid increases in A_{525} and a grey appearance early in the reaction indicate the formation of nanoparticles that are not transferrable into chloroform using 1-dodecanethiol, while “log-shaped” curves generated by solutions that slowly turn from clear to pink indicate the formation of nanoparticles that are transferrable.

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4. Discussion

We have shown that time-resolved spectroscopic measurement of solutions of gold nanoparticles during synthesis is useful in characterization. Specifically, the shape of the A_{525} vs. time curves for the synthesis of AuNP contains information that is useful not only in discerning the mechanism of synthesis but also in predicting their behavior concerning phase transfer. In the future, the first derivatives of these absorbance vs. time curves will be investigated to determine if these derivatives provide a more straightforward method for comparing the AuNP products formed by chemical reduction syntheses.

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Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at: www.mdpi.com/xxx/s1, Video of synthesis of gold nanoparticles, Raw data for Figure 2, Raw data for Figure 4.

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259
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261
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263
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268